

Performance of different aeration strategies for biological nutrient removal and the mitigation of N₂O emissions

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Abstract

Aerobic granular sludge (AGS) represents a sustainable alternative to conventional biological wastewater treatment, as it allows simultaneous nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) removal with a reduced dissolved oxygen (DO) and carbon demand, and improved settleability. Emissions of the greenhouse gas nitrous oxide (N₂O) are a major challenge for the sustainability of this technology. The aeration is a key operational parameter with a strong influence on the dynamics of N₂O formation, reduction, and emission. This study aims to evaluate the long-term performance and stability of two different aeration strategies. Under alternating aerobic and anoxic conditions, a DO of 2 – 4 mg O₂·L⁻¹ was found unfavorable for a stable PAO community, while 1 – 3 mg O₂·L⁻¹ resulted in rapid stabilization. This strategy was characterized by pronounced N₂O formation and stripping during aerobic steps. Continuous low aeration with an average DO of 0.5 mg O₂·L⁻¹ was found beneficial for stable P removal, high efficiency of simultaneous nitrification and (shortcut) denitrification (SND), and low N₂O levels. The two aeration strategies resulted in notable differences in the microbial communities of nitrifiers and denitrifiers, which are decisive for N₂O production.

Keywords

Aeration strategy, aerobic granular sludge, biological nutrient removal, greenhouse gas, N₂O

INTRODUCTION

Nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions represent one of the major challenges of wastewater treatment, often accounting for more than half of the carbon footprint of treatment plants (Maktabifard et al., 2022). The N₂O yield of AGS systems is highly variable, with values reported in literature ranging from less than 1 % to more than 20 % of the influent total nitrogen load (Pan et al., 2024). A multitude of microorganisms were proposed to contribute; Dockx et al. (2021) recently suggested a correlation between the abundance of *Accumulibacter* and N₂O emissions. With denitrification in AGS relying on intragranular oxygen gradients, the DO concentration is a key parameters controlling N₂O formation and emission (Daigger & Littleton, 2014). This study evaluates the long-term performance and N₂O dynamics of two SBR systems applying different aeration strategies: alternating biological nutrient removal (ABNR-EBPR) and simultaneous nitrification, denitrification, and phosphorus removal (SNDPR).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two identical double-walled sequencing batch reactors (SBRs) with a working volume of 12 L were seeded with flocculent sludge from a low-loaded municipal wastewater treatment plant and operated for 200 days. The design was similar to the setup described by Dockx et al. (2021). Both SBRs received 1000 mL/cycle of an identical synthetic influent with a chemical oxygen demand (COD) of 1800 mg COD·L⁻¹ (50 % acetate and 50 % propionate), COD/N = 18, and

COD/P = 60. The 6h treatment cycles of both SBRs are presented in Figure 1. Interval aeration was used to control the DO at 2.0 – 4.0 mg O₂·L⁻¹ in SBR 1 and 0.4 – 0.6 mg O₂·L⁻¹ in SBR 2.

SBR 1	Feed	Anaerobic	Aerobic	Anoxic	Aerobic	Settle/Decant
	10	90	46	58	120	36
SBR 2	Feed	Anaerobic	Aerobic (low DO)			Settle/Decant
	10	90	224			36

Figure 1. Cycle setup and step durations (in minutes) of the two operated SBRs.

Analyses. Sludge and water testing were performed weekly. The sludge analysis included the determination of the biomass concentration, the sludge volume index (SVI), and microscopic inspection. 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing was performed by DNAsense ApS (Aalborg, Denmark), using the MiDAS 5.2 database for taxonomic classification. Parameters determined for influent, effluent, and cycle samples were COD and soluble COD (sCOD), dissolved organic carbon (DOC), nutrients (NH₄-N, NO₂-N, NO₃-N, PO₄-P), total nitrogen (TN), total phosphorus (TP), and total suspended solids (TSS). In-situ measurements were supported by nitrifier activity and electron acceptor batch experiments. The N₂O concentration was measured in-situ and in the reactor off-gas using Clark-type N₂O microsensors (Unisense A/S, Denmark). Off-gas was captured using a customized floating hood connected to a measurement cell.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Dense granules developed in both reactors, as shown in Figure 2. A median particle size (D₅₀) of 200 μm was exceeded in both systems after 60 days. By the end of the study period, D₅₀ was 750 μm in SBR 1 and 1030 μm in SBR 2. The largest particle fraction (D₉₀) reached > 1.5 mm in SBR 1 and > 2 mm SBR 2. The low DO regime in SBR 2 thus resulted in the formation of larger granules compared to the ABNR system in SBR 1, facilitating the establishment of anoxic micro-environments required for SND. After day 60, no in-situ accumulation of NO₃-N and NO₂-N was observed in SBR 2, along with SND efficiencies of 97.79 ± 4.29 %. In SBR 1, concurrent granule formation and breakage resulted in the co-existence of large granules and fine particles, with the smallest fraction (D₁₀) remaining virtually unchanged below 60 μm, while D₁₀ exceeded 500 μm in SBR 2. In consequence, SBR 2 was characterized by a superior settling performance of SVI₃₀/SVI₁₀ = 1.00, compared to 0.76 in SBR 1.

Figure 2. Sludge morphology development (bright field, scale bar = 500 μm).

Microbial communities

Accumulibacter were enriched in both SBR systems and remained the only present PAO. Their relative abundance (RA) was more stable and higher in SBR 2 (max. RA = 22.9 %) than SBR 1 (max. RA = 14.3 %), coinciding with the superior sludge morphology. *Midas_g_1328*, a common genus in Belgian industrial treatment plants (Seguel Suazo et al., 2024), was the most abundant organism in SBR 1, accounting for up to 26.7 % of the biomass. Although little is

known about this genus *in situ*, its dominance suggests a relationship with the observed granule instability in SBR 1. The nitrifier and denitrifier communities were strongly influenced by the different aeration strategies. While the genus *Nitrospira*, known for being able to perform full nitrification (Daims et al., 2015), was enriched to > 5 % in SBR 1, the AOB *Nitrosomonas* dominated in SBR 2. Along with the disappearance of *Nitrospira* from SBR 2, respirometric essays performed on day 71 revealed a NOB/AOB activity ratio of 0.39 ± 0.04 , indicating the suppression of NOB. On day 145, no more NOB activity was registered, suggesting shortcut denitrification via nitrite. In SBR 1, the peak abundance of *Nitrospira* coincided with a high NOB/AOB ratio of 1.60 ± 0.17 . The denitrifier community in SBR 1 was dominated by *Thauera*, while *Denitratisoma* was the most abundant denitrifier in SBR 2.

Performance of different aeration strategies

Nutrient removal. Stable TN removal was achieved by both systems, with efficiencies of 92.70 ± 1.42 % in SBR 1 and 94.25 ± 2.02 % in SBR 2. TP removal reached 83.92 ± 14.23 % in SBR 1 compared to 92.18 ± 5.69 % in SBR 2, reflecting the lower abundance and higher variability of *Accumulibacter* in this system. However, the low aeration in SBR 2 was more prone to technical incidents, which could cause rapid P release and accumulation in the effluent. Nonetheless, P removal quickly stabilized once the aeration was re-established, demonstrating the resilience of the PAO community. While aerobic periods of $2 - 4$ mg O₂·L⁻¹ were applied in SBR 1, P removal was highly variable, characterized by alternating periods of accumulation and removal. Reducing the aeration limits to $1 - 3$ mg O₂·L⁻¹ on day 114 resulted in a rapid stabilization of the TP removal efficiency, reaching 91.84 ± 5.94 % after the change.

Denitrifying PAO activity. DO remained the preferred electron acceptor for PAOs in both SBR systems, according to batch tests (see Table 1). Both sludges further established dPAO activity using nitrate, demonstrating the potential of *Accumulibacter* for anoxic P removal. However, the low P uptake with nitrite suggests that PAOs did not play a key role for denitrification in SBR 2 *in situ*, as nitrifier activity tests and the absence of NOB indicate limited *in-situ* nitrate formation. Hence, other denitrifiers such as *Denitratisoma* presumably reduced nitrite produced by *Nitrosomonas*, while aerobic P removal was performed concurrently.

Table 1. Average PO₄-P uptake within 120 min during batch tests with individual electron acceptors throughout the study period. All samples were first spiked with 150 mg COD·L⁻¹ (50 % acetate, 50 % propionate) and exposed to 90 min of anaerobic conditions.

	PO ₄ -P uptake in 120 min with electron acceptor (mg PO ₄ -P · VSS ⁻¹)		
	DO	NO ₃ -N	NO ₂ -N
SBR 1	12.84 ± 2.38	6.35 ± 2.13	2.60 ± 1.08
SBR 2	14.14 ± 0.47	6.45 ± 0.44	0.84 ± 0.78

N₂O formation and emission. Dissolved and off-gas N₂O profiles are presented in Figure 3. In SBR 1, aerobic N₂O formation and stripping were strongly pronounced. Anoxic peaks of up to 1.0 mg N₂O-N·L⁻¹, likely stimulated by *in-situ* nitrite accumulation during nitrification, had limited contribution to emissions. The N₂O levels in SBR 2 increased gradually during aeration, but remained significantly lower than in SBR 1. For the last two weeks of operation, emissions were estimated based on the off-gas N₂O concentration profiles and the average measured gas flow rate. In line with the *in-situ* concentrations, SBR 1 demonstrated considerably higher N₂O emissions of 8.26 ± 2.59 %TN, compared to 2.20 ± 0.81 %TN emitted from SBR 2.

Figure 3. Dissolved and off-gas $\text{N}_2\text{O-N}$ profiles of both SBRs at the end of the study period.

CONCLUSION

Two different aeration strategies were analyzed regarding their impact on sludge morphology, nutrient removal, and N_2O emissions. Under an alternating aeration regime, excess oxygen adversely influenced the size and stability of granules, as well as the P removal performance. N removal and N_2O formation in the two systems were governed by substantially different nitrifier and denitrifier communities. Denitrifying PAOs were likely not involved in N_2O formation during SNDPR. The presented results enhance the understanding of nutrient removal and N_2O formation dynamics in AGS, contributing to more sustainable wastewater treatment.

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